

The TAPIRO research reactor modelling as a point: some reactor physics evaluations on TAPIRO in the spirit of Mario Carta's research work and guidance

Dulla S.¹, Aimetta A.¹, Gilad E.²

¹Politecnico di Torino, DENERG, NEMO Group, Torino, Italy;
²Ben-Gurion University of the Negev, Beer sheva 8410501, Israel

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ABSTRACT

The TAPIRO research reactor, located at the ENEA Casaccia laboratories, is an experimental facility characterized by unique properties, due to its compact dimensions and composition that allows access to an almost pure fission spectrum and different fast spectrum configurations of interest, especially in light of the present significant interest in the development of fast reactor technology. In this work, the point-like behavior of TAPIRO, a feature that allows for the safe testing of methods for fast reactor analysis in a controlled configuration, is studied and confirmed through the analysis of simulated pulsed experiments obtained from MCNP simulations.

Keywords: TAPIRO, Point Kinetics, Pulsed Experiments, Area Method

1. INTRODUCTION

TAPIRO is a fast neutron source nuclear reactor located at the ENEA Casaccia Research Centre near Rome. The reactor design is based on the Argonne Fast Source Reactor – Idaho Falls [1], it was built in the 60s and achieved first criticality in 1971. The facility's key components include a cylindrical core of highly enriched metallic uranium (98.5% U; 1.5% Mo) with stainless steel cladding, surrounded by a cylindrical copper structure acting as a reflector, housed in a steel sheath surrounded by a biological shield of borated concrete. Being a research facility, TAPIRO is equipped with several irradiation channels crossing the reflector and reaching positions very close to the inner core (see Figure 1, from [2]).

Figure 1. TAPIRO irradiation facilities [2].

The Italian acronym stands for Taratura Pila RApida potenza zero = Reference Fast Pile at Zero Power. This name summarizes efficiently one of the main features of TAPIRO that makes this experimental facility unique in the International framework of research reactors, i.e., the possibility to access an almost pure neutron fission spectrum via the diametral channel crossing the core, thus allowing irradiation and measures that are particularly significant in the current significant effort on the development of fast reactor technology.

TAPIRO is one of the two research reactors (the other one is the TRIGA-RC1) at the ENEA Casaccia center that is managed by the "Laboratorio Reattori Nucleari di Ricerca. Dr. Mario Carta has been head of this laboratory from almost 10 years, till 2022 when he retired. It was thanks to his enlightened scientific vision, his pro-activity and keen interest to cooperate with other "reactor physics enthusiasts" that we all were progressively involved in various studies on the TAPIRO reactor (see e.g. [3-4]), with the explicit intent in strengthening pre-existing cooperation and fully exploit the potential of TAPIRO as a research facility in support of a variety of studies, with a specific focus on the TAPIRO representativity of the neutronic behavior in fast reactors.

This work presents a study on TAPIRO to characterize the validity of the point kinetics assumption, carried out following the approach and spirit that Mario always adopted in his research work: looking for the simplicity to clearly highlight the physical phenomena.

2. THE POINT KINETIC REPRESENTATION OF A REACTOR

Point Kinetics (PK) is a zero-dimensional model that is widely adopted for the description of the neutron time-dependent behavior, especially in the frame of multiphysics and system codes, as it allows fast-running evaluations, although at the cost of a strongly approximated representation of the reactor core behavior. In the field of experimental reactor physics, PK has served as the starting point for a series of models for interpreting measurements, such as those tailored for monitoring reactivity [5] or the entire class of methods based on neutron noise [6]. It is therefore clear that the applicability of the point-like hypothesis heavily impacts the accuracy of the results produced with such methods.

Mario Carta, during his long career, has tackled reactor physics problems of various types, ranging from more theoretical questions to the challenges of realistic applications. In particular, his research activity has been focused for many years on the development of subcritical, Accelerator-Driven Systems (ADS), and the topic of the representativity of point kinetics when interpreting experimental measures has been a *leitmotif* of his work for many years [7-8]. When becoming the head of the laboratory where TAPIRO is located, we also had the opportunity to discuss at length the possibility to apply methodology developed for reactivity monitoring, such as the MAQTA method [9], to TAPIRO, or the interest in developing an experimental campaign on neutron noise to test such approaches in a fast neutron spectrum.

With Mario's sudden passing, we have all lost a precious colleague and friend, and a wise man who was able to kindly direct all scientific discussions to a positive outcome. We are now trying to keep on pursuing all the scientific quests we discussed in the past, and in this work we tackle the underlying question: is the PK assumption safely applicable when interpreting experiments in the TAPIRO reactor? We are approaching this question exploiting the previous experience on reactivity monitoring methods, in particular the Area Method (AM): flux signals, mimicking the TAPIRO response to a source pulse, have been generated with a detailed Monte Carlo model of TAPIRO and the interpretation of the results with AM allows us to perform some evaluations on the point-like behavior of TAPIRO.

3. THE AREA METHOD AND ITS APPLICATION TO TAPIRO

3.1. Physical and Mathematical Foundations of the Area Method

In subcritical nuclear systems, accurate reactivity measurement can be achieved using an established and widely used technique, such as the area method [5]. The area method works by analyzing the time-

dependent behavior of the neutron population following a train of short neutron pulses with period T , with the assumption of reaching a dynamic equilibrium between the prompt and delayed neutron populations. The system's reactivity can be inferred by separating and integrating the contributions from prompt and delayed neutrons over a single period between two source pulses.

In fact, it is assumed that, when dynamic equilibrium is reached, the total neutron population during the period can be expressed as:

$$n(t) = n_p(t) + n_d \quad (1)$$

The integration of this signal, separating the two contributions, provides an expression for the estimation of the reactivity in dollars (see Figure 2):

$$\rho/\beta_{\text{eff}} = -A_p/A_d \quad (2)$$

Figure 2. Illustration of the prompt A_p (yellow) and delayed A_d (lavender) areas [11].

In a real system, where neutron behavior may significantly differ from the point kinetic assumption, the results obtained with the area method can be remarkably different when applied to detector signals in different positions. Various methods have been developed in such cases to adjust the various reactivity estimations towards more consistent results [10]. In the present work, we aim to assess the point-like behavior of TAPIRO by observing how close or different the reactivity estimations are obtained by analyzing different detector signals in the two cores. Larger differences in the reactivity values will be significant for a core with less point-like behavior.

3.2. Monte Carlo Simulation of the Source Pulse

In the absence of real experimental signals in TAPIRO, Monte Carlo simulations, based on a detailed model of the reactor, have been performed to provide suitable signals for applying the area method. In this approach the specifics of the source device (which is constituted by an accelerator impinging on a target in many ADS designs) are not included in the model, as well as the detection system model, focusing solely on the estimation of some reaction rates. The system is driven by an external deuterium-deuterium (D-D) pulsed neutron source located at $(0, 0, -5.44)$, where the z axis is centered at the top of the core, and the x and y coordinates are centered in corresponding to the tangential channel that is placed right outside the fissile region.

The source emits neutrons over a single pulse duration of 5 microseconds, followed by the shut-down of the reactor involving all the time scales of the prompt and delayed neutrons. The core configuration has been set in subcritical mode, by moving the control devices, and the corresponding kinetic parameters are shown in Table I. The simulation recorded fission reaction rates in U-235 and U-238

fission chamber-like point detectors (MCNP F5 Tally). The coordinates of the detectors are shown in Table II. Considering the limited dimension of the U-235 core (cylinder with height and diameter around 15 cm), the detector positions have been chosen compatibly with the positions that are experimentally accessible, trying to explore different conditions of proximity or distance from the fissile region.

Table I. Kinetic parameters of TAPIRO evaluated for the MC model adopted.

k_{eff}	Λ	β_{eff}
0.98249 ± 0.00002	47.65 ± 0.11 ns	674 ± 2 pcm

Table II. Coordinates of the fission rate point detectors.

DET 1	0, 0, 0
DET 2	0, 21.4, 0
DET 3	10.6, 0, 5
DET 4	10.6, 18, 5
DET 5	9.05, 0, 0
DET 6	21.4, 0, 0

3.3. Results and Analysis

The normalized reaction rates recorded in the U-235 and U-238 detectors are shown in Figure 3. As the MC simulation does not provide the actual response to a pulse train, but to a single pulse only, a method to reconstruct the corresponding equilibrium contributions of delayed neutrons, originally developed by Talamo and Gohar and adopted in [11], has been here used to elaborate the provided signal:

$$n(t) = n_{MC}(t) + \frac{1}{T} \int_T^{\infty} n_{MC}(t') dt' \quad \text{for } t \in [0, T] \quad (3)$$

where the signal produced by MC is integrated in time beyond the period T and this term, divided by the period T , provides the additional contribution accounting for the delayed neutrons in equilibrium over the period.

Figure 3. Normalized reaction rates recorded in the U-235 and U-238 detectors after a 5 μ s neutron pulse.

Once the AM is applied to all these signals, having exploited formula (3), the reactivity evaluations obtained are summarized in Table III, together with the reference subcriticality level obtained in the MC calculation.

Table III. AM reactivity evaluations and deviation from the reference at multiple spatial points and assuming different energy sensitivities (U-235 vs. U-238 detectors).

Ref. ρ (pcm)	Detector type	Detector No.	AM reactivity (pcm)	$\Delta\rho$ (pcm)	$\Delta\rho$ (%)
-1782	U-235	1	-1785	-3	-0.2
		2	-1793	-11	-0.6
		3	-1763	20	1.1
		4	-1780	2	0.1
		5	-1778	4	0.2
	U-238	6	-1785	-3	-0.2
		1	-1858	-76	-4.3
		2	-1834	-52	-2.9
		3	-1782	0	0.0
		4	-1835	-53	-3.0
		5	-1815	-11	-0.6
		6	-1822	-40	-2.2

The reactivity was measured using two types of neutron detectors – U-235 and U-238 point fission chambers – placed at six different spatial locations. The U-235 detectors are primarily sensitive to thermal and epithermal neutrons (although they are also influenced by fast fission), while the U-238 detectors respond to fast neutrons only.

The U-235 detector measurements show excellent agreement with the reference reactivity of -1782 pcm, with relative deviations consistently within $\pm 1.1\%$ (mostly under $\pm 0.3\%$) and an average deviation of 0.4%. These results suggest that TAPIRO is highly point-like over the entire neutron spectrum. The spatial variation is minimal, even at detector positions such as (0, 21.4, 0) and (13.6, 0, 5), which are displaced from both the source location at (0, 0, -5.44) and the core center.

The U-238 detectors, focusing on the response to fast neutrons show slightly higher deviations, which is anyway consistent with the different energy distribution in the fast range especially when getting closet to the D-D source (DET1). On the basis of these results, it can be stated that TAPIRO is approximately a point in the thermal/epithermal range, with some spatial and spectral non-uniformities in the fast spectrum.

To give additional context to the present set of results, we may refer to a similar experimental analysis, performed on the facility VENUS-F at SCK CEN, where the SC-1 configuration in the presence of a pulsed source was analyzed with different methods based on point kinetics. The results, presented in [12], showed AM results characterized by variations among detector locations up to 63cents, with a $\beta_{eff} = 722$ pcm leading to $\Delta\rho_{max} = 455$ pcm. Such significant discrepancies in the reactivity estimation led to the necessity to apply suitable adjustment methodologies, accounting for the spatial/spectral effects PK is not able to model, with a visible improvement of the results, although such adjustment methods are strongly system-dependent. In the VENUS-F case, it was also observed that larger discrepancies were obtained both in detectors that were in the reflector, but also in a detector in the core, very close to the source location. In this last case, the physical intuition suggests that the signal generated by neutrons directly emerging from the source, thus not interacting with the core material to gain information on the reactor characteristics, is affecting the quality of the reactivity prediction.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The TAPIRO reactor is an experimental facility with very large potential for reactor physics analysis and application of experimental methodologies that can become extremely interesting in the context of fast reactor technology development. Mario Carta, while he was the head of the ENEA laboratory where TAPIRO is located, has always been a very strong and vocal supporter of this facility, expanding the fields of scientific collaborations and the potential uses of TAPIRO for the International community. Among these actions, Mario engaged us in devising new experimental activities and possible uses of TAPIRO that could be of interest for the reactor physics community.

In this work, we performed an assessment of the characteristics of TAPIRO, focusing on the point-like behavior of this facility, to assess this property with an approach based on the use of the Area Method, which we believe Mario would have appreciated due to his experience with the use of methods for reactivity estimation and for the “simplicity” of the approach to highlight physical properties.

TAPIRO, being a reactor with a remarkable point-like behavior, is therefore a very suitable facility to test methods based on this assumption. This aspect, in association with the significance of the neutron energy spectrum for fast reactor-related studies, opens the possibility of devising new experimental campaigns in TAPIRO, such as the use of this unique facility to test the application of neutron noise techniques in a fast neutron spectrum.

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REFERENCES

- [1] P. I. Amundson, W. G. Davey, R. N. Curran, G. S. Brunson, R. J. Huber. “Reactor Physics Measurements in the Argonne Fast Source Reactor”. In *Proceedings of International Conference on the Utilization of Research Reactors and Reactor Mathematics and Computation*, Mexico, 2-4 May (1967).
- [2] M. Carta, M. Cesaroni et al. “Research Reactors for the development of materials and fuels for innovative nuclear energy systems”. *IAEA NUCLEAR ENERGY SERIES NO. NP-T-5.8*, International Atomic Energy Agency, Vienna (2017). IAEAL 17-01107, ISBN 978-92-0-100816-9.

- [3] C. Di Gesare, D. Caron, S. Dulla, P. Ravetto, M. Carta, V. Fabrizio, "Use of new nuclear data libraries for the Monte Carlo analysis of neutronic measurements in the TAPIRO reactor". In *International conference PHYSOR 2018*, Cancun, Mexico (2018).
- [4] M. Carta, N. Burgio, V. Fabrizio, L. Falconi, V. Peluso, A. Santagata, S. Dulla, "A Revisitation of the ENEA TAPIRO Fast Source Reactor Neutronic Capabilities". In *International conference PHYSOR 2022*, Pittsburgh, PA (2022).
- [5] N. Sjostrand. "Measurements on a subcritical reactor using a pulsed neutron source". *Archiv for Fysik*, **11**, 233-246 (1956).
- [6] E. Gilad, A. Kolin, O. Rivin, C. Dubi, B. Geslot and P. Blaise. "Analysis of critical and subcritical neutron noise experiments in MINERVE reactor using advanced noise techniques". In *Physics of Reactors 2016, PHYSOR 2016: Unifying Theory and Experiments in the 21st Century*, Idaho Falls, ID (2016).
- [7] W. Uyttenhove, P. Baeten, G. Van Den Eynde, A. Kochetkov, D. Lathouwers, M. Carta. "The neutronic design of a critical lead reflected zero-power reference core for on-line subcriticality measurements in Accelerator Driven Systems". *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **38**, 1519-1526 (2011).
- [8] G. Glinatsis, M. Carta, D. Gugiu. "Conceptual design of a sub-critical Pb-cooled Accelerator Driven System (ADS) fuelled by (Th-LEU)", *Annals of Nuclear Energy*. **104**, 1-8 (2017).
- [9] S. Dulla, S. S. Hoh, G. Marana, M. Nervo, P. Ravetto, C. H. Pyeon. "Analysis of KUCA measurements by the reactivity monitoring MAQTA method". *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **101**, 397-407 (2017).
- [10] M. Carta, A. D'Angelo, V. Peluso, G. Aliberti, P. Palmiotti, J.-F. Lebrat, C. Destouches. "Reactivity assessment and spatial time-effects from the MUSE kinetics experiments". In *PHYSOR 2004 - The Physics of Fuel Cycles and Advanced Nuclear Systems: Global Developments*, Chicago, USA (2004).
- [11] A. Talamo, Y. Gohar, F. Gabrielli, A. Rineiski, C. Pyeon. "Advances in the computation of the Sjöstrand, Rossi, and Feynman distributions". *Progress in Nuclear Energy*, **101**, 299-311 (2017).
- [12] S. Dulla, M. Nervo, P. Ravetto, G. Mila, S. Argirò, S. Beolè, M. Masera, G. Bianchini, M. Carta, V. Fabrizio, V. Peluso, F. Gabrielli, A. Rineiski, A. Kochetkov, P. Baeten, W. Uyttenhove, G. Vittiglio, J. Wagemans. "Intepretation of experimental measurements on the SC-1 configuration of the VENUS-F core". In *Proceedings of PHYSOR2014*, Kyoto, Japan (2014).